

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15687238

Smart Skill Acquisition Programme: A Panacea For Entrepreneurial Development Among Youths In Anambra State, Nigeria

Dr. Chineze J. Jacobs* & Jude Micheal

Department of Entrepreneurship Studies

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State Nigeria

Corresponding Author: cj.jacobs@coou.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of smart skill acquisition programme: a panacea for entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria. The objective of the study is to access the effect of technical skill, youth empowerment and infrastructural development on entrepreneurial development among the youths in Anambra state, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used to conduct the study. Multiple Regression analysis and descriptive statistics with the aid of SPSS version 23 were used for data analysis and test of hypothesis which established the extent of relationship between independent variable and dependent variable of the study. The finding revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between technical skill, Youth empowerment and infrastructural development on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra, state Nigeria. The study recommended that efforts should be intensified to boost technical skill education and training in the state by the government at all levels. This could be made possible through the provision of well-equipped skill acquisition centres in the state to be funded by special intervention fund dedicated for the programme.

Keywords: Technical skill, Youth empowerment, infrastructural development, entrepreneurial development, youths

INTRODUCTION

Skill acquisition is a strong source of wealth creation that helps to improve the minds of youth towards entrepreneurial development in an environment that is competitive and business oriented like Nigeria. This programme serves as mechanism for poverty alleviation, job creation, business concept innovation, productivity and risk taking among others.

Skills acquisition programme is a program designed to provide the ability among individual to exploit opportunity and create an enterprise whether big or small not only for personal gains but also for social and developmental gains (Olugunju, 2016). Oboreh (2019) defined skill acquisition as the ability to create something new with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. Skills are required through training that emphasizes the acquisition and development of appropriate knowledge and experience that will enable individual to maximize the resources around him within the limit of his capability. It further consists of effective utilization of ideas, information and facts that helps a learner develop competences needed for business career commitment such as setting up business, marketing, services or being productive, wealth creators, employers of labour and self-reliant thereby contributing to nation building.

Globally, skills acquisition programmes introduced into educational institutions were meant to provide the level of knowledge and skills needed to exploit entrepreneurial opportunities which could help the economic development of a given nation (Abayomi & Odozi, 2014). In line with this, the government has put in place several skills acquisition programmes, including the introduction of entrepreneurship courses and establishment of vocational and skill acquisition centers and departments in institutions of higher learning across the states. The aim of such programmes were to impact skills, attitude, aspirations, competencies and creativity mostly in the youths and micro credit, to enable them practice entrepreneurship and create self employment as well as help generate employment for others (Muhd, 2016).

Skill acquisition is the main key that is geared towards improving the life and economic status of youths through entrepreneurial promotion and development. The human capital found in youths is a vital determinant of long term economic survival and growth sustainability that a nation can invest heavily. However, making sure that youths are prepared for their entrepreneurial spirit is important to the course of entrepreneurial skill development and job creation. Youth unemployment is a global issue that the government all over the world is contending with. As a result, there is an increasing demand for skill programme to create entrepreneurs in the world today (Aun et al 2018). Countries world over are trying to lure entrepreneurs who can create their own capital in order to enhance economic growth. The level of unemployment in Nigeria and economic hardship seems to have continued to escalate despite various measures and tactics that the government has adopted over the years (Anyu & Amadi, 2016).

The youths can be considered as the strength and backbone of any country. They are the future hope in most of all spheres of economic development which a nation aspires to attain. Youths account for about 65% of the Nigeria labour force and are expected to contribute about 73% of the nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (NDE, 2015). Youths entrepreneurial development and their economic empowerment are vital stages in life for the building of human capital that allows young people to gain creativity, innovativeness and to eradicate poverty and joblessness. Skill acquisition schemes is vital determinant of long term growth that a nation can invest on. Furthermore, making sure that youths are well prepared for the future is necessary to the course of entrepreneurial development in any country. (Isaac et al 2018).

Skill acquisition has become an essential bailout for youths' self-employability and the attainment of entrepreneurial spirit among the unemployed youths (Paul, 2017). Skill acquisition programmes serves as a viable mechanism that provides solid foundation for self-employability and business creativity in a multi-ethnic and high populated nation like Nigeria. Government is not capable of accommodating youths unemployed as a result, numerous social problems came up which help in degrading the value and status of the nation from a global perception. Such as kidnapping, armed banditry, Boko haram, Cybercrime, Cultism, armed robbery to mention but a few. Skill acquisition remains the viable option to address these problems by inculcating and enhancing entrepreneurial spirit among youths to become self-employed, self-creative, enhance business concept, innovation and poverty reduction. These help youth to develop their businesses, pursue their dreams positively and contribute to overall productive capacity and national development (Efe-Imafidon et al, 2017).

However, skill acquisition is defined as acquiring knowledge and expertise in skills that enhance the youths' personal livelihood through their involvement in enduring business startup, that can further enhance employment opportunity, and promoting economic development and growth. It is against this background that the study seeks to determine the extent of relationship between skills acquisition and entrepreneurial development among the teeming youths in Anambra State. It attempts to explore the need to equip the youths with viable and employable skills necessary for transforming them towards creativity, innovativeness, risk taking, poverty reduction, self-employment and business management skills instead of relying on office or white collar-jobs.

Statement of Problem

Increasing rate of poor entrepreneurial spirit among the youths in Nigeria has resulted in growing wave of crimes in the society as the youths continue to battle for survival with social and economic difficulties affecting the totality of our nation. Steve (2018), opines that when the teeming youths are not gainfully

creative, innovative and employed in both private and public sector, they become vulnerable to criminality such as kidnapping, terrorism, rape, rituals/yahoo boys plus which have become the latest phenomenon among our youths today, armed robbery and many other social vices. Essay (2018) states that skills acquisition scheme help youths not to only become job creators but wealth creators and it leads to wealth accumulation and contribute immensely in reducing unemployment among the youths.

Problems of unemployment continue to soar high in Anambra state due to disparity between market requirement and skills that are offered to teeming unemployed youths. The major problem of Anambra state appears to be lingering unemployment and increase redundancy of vast proportion of youths (Dandago, 2014). Bala (2020) noted that the level of insecurity and joblessness seems to have continued to increase despite entrepreneurial skill measures taken by the government of Anambra state.

Over the years, various training skills centers have been introduced to transform the teeming youths towards entrepreneurial achievement in the state, very little have been achieved in that regards. This is because the youths have not been introduced to skill acquisition that is sustainable, marketable, innovative and creative. Their potentials have not been fully developed to the level of technical skills capable of instilling creativity, innovativeness and self-employment. The major problem is disparity between labour market requirements and skills training offered by Anambra state owned skills acquisition centres. This mismatch is the central problem militating against employability of youths in the state. The state focuses on simple and less attractive skills but the markets demand technical skills training that is innovative and offer sustainable employment and self-reliant advantage.

This is apparent because high rate of insecurity in Anambra State among the youths is on the increase. Youths attack innocent people on their ways and collect valuables on daily basis. Redundancy and drug addictions e.gmkpurumiri etc among the youths is high, political thuggery is also on the increase. The situation is becoming uncontrollable and not manageable by the state and federal authorities.

Observation revealed that skills acquisition centers were functional with relative high number of participants but still redundant and crime is still very high in the state. It was equally observed that vast proportion of youths who graduated from various centers and instructions are still not employed. Despite the numerous efforts from the state government, gap still exist because there is an urgent need to draw the attention of the government and stakeholders towards technically oriented skills that are sustainable that will make the youths to be marketably attractive, innovative and self employed.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to determine the effect of skill acquisition programme on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra State. Specifically, the study will examine;

- i. The effect of technical skills on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria
- ii. The effect of youth empowerment on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria
- iii. The effect of infrastructural development on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra State.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

To overcome the problem and accomplish the objective of the study, the following hypotheses was formulated.

H₀₁: Technical skill acquisition does not affect entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria

H₀₁: Youth empowerment has no significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria

H₀₁: There is no significant effect between infrastructural development and entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Smart Skill Acquisition

Smart skills are construed to mean the ability of all individuals to acquire more proactive and or special ability for resolution of a particular situation or challenges. Skill acquisition programmes are therefore, process involving skill upgrading and economic subsistence of the nation (Solaja & Adenuga 2016). It is also seen to embody various creative measures of developing basic and strategic ideas of becoming self-employed or self-reliant as a result of acquiring something special. In other perspective, skills acquisition programmes are empowerment strategies that are expected to imbibe or produce the spirit of craftsmanship and entrepreneurship in the youths particularly unemployed graduates to make them job creators instead of job seekers.

In addition, Smart skills acquisition programme is a factor of empowerment encircling processes of improving human potentials and capacities through vocational, technical entrepreneurial exercise that aim at teaching individuals on how best to make use of their hands, minds and thoughts to earn better standard of living, generate job opportunities and contribute positively to the development process of the society. In other words, skill acquisition programmes are knowledge building programmes involving the application of theory and practical methods of training to develop not only practical skills but also the right attitudes and mindset for achieving national development through making youths to become productive and business creators (Oguchi, 2020). Smart Skill acquisition translates to development of SMEs and sometimes larger scale business based on creativity and innovation as products of entrepreneurial development (Okegbemiro & Alao, 2016). Skill acquisition also assist efficiently in lessening poverty, enhance creativity and business startup among youths with working age through innovation, creation and expansion of business ventures. Similarly, Smart skill acquisition programmes aimed to instill innovation spirit among the teeming youths. It has the capacity to reduce crime rate and criminal intentions by engaging unproductive and unemployed through self-employment or job creation.

2.1.2 Entrepreneurial Development

Entrepreneurial development has been found to be capable of making positive impact on the economy of a nation and the quality of life of the people especially the unemployed youths. However, it is seen that only business firms and individuals that have been able to adopt and put into practice the concept of creativity, business innovations are able to impact the economy and national development and add positively to the welfare of youths. Businesses that embrace changes and concept innovation are able to respond and adapt to the present circumstances. Entrepreneurial development stem from the high rate of unemployment, high level of poverty and slow economic growth rate in Nigeria. Entrepreneurial development is the key to poverty eradication, employment generation and rapid economic development (Anigbogu, Onwuteaka & Okoli, 2019).

However, entrepreneurial development has helped in shaping the economy of most of the advance and developed nations of the world. Innovativeness, business startup, skills, new business, creativity, risk taking, job creation, productivity to name a few are the product of entrepreneurial development through skill acquisition, training and teaching. This concept has been a topical issue in Africa and the rest of the world because of the significant and critical roles entrepreneurial spirit has played in building most of the advanced and emerging markets (Anigbogu et al, 2019). Furthermore, entrepreneurial development in any nation plays critical role in contributing to economic viability and growth, job creation, as well as national income development. The concept of entrepreneurial development involves creating of incremental wealth. The wealth is created through skills development by youths who assume the major risk in terms of equity, time and career commitment or provide value for some products or services, but value should somehow be infused by entrepreneurs through receiving and locating necessary skills

2.1.6 Youth

The term youth has been variously defined. Ndu (2000) and Yusuf (2001) saw youths as neither adolescents nor children characterized by excessive energy that needs to be exerted, which if not guarded, is channeled into negative tendencies. The United Nations General Assembly and World Bank cited in

Adewuyi (2008) defined the youth as people between ages 15 to 24 years. In Nigeria, the people within the age limit of 30 years are considered as youths hence they are allowed to participate in the National Youth Service Scheme (NYSC). Youths are filled with energy and when this energy is positively channeled or guarded, they are highly productive, and hence they are likely to contribute to the overall development of the society.

Similarly, Youth” is classified as the young people between the ages of 15-24 years (ILO, 2010). These also depend on individual country to country on who they call youth. Hence, over 1.2 billion youth globally, that are about 80% dwell in third world countries, with 60% in Asia, and 17% in Africa (14% from sub-Saharan Africa and 3% from North Africa). The NYDP (2001) defines youth as people aged 18-35. They constitute about 40% of the more than 140 million people of Nigeria. 2006 population census revealed that 45.4 million of Nigeria populace are youth between the ages of 10 – 24 indicating 34% of the entire population.

2.1.3 Technical Skill Training

Skill is noteworthy in everybody’s life. Many technicians earn more than some school graduates because they acquire more practical skills than the theories unlike the graduates who were sustained with theoretical encounters while in the universities. Technical skill is the ability to be prepared on a particular task or work and become expert in it. As of now, numerous graduates in the nation are still jobless due to long system of education that is more theoretical than practical learning. The reason for high rate of unemployment amongst the vibrant youths in our society today is due to lack of skill to add up to what they learnt from their various institutions. Skill acquisition is a major tool for extreme poverty eradication and hunger with the aim of creating an avenue for jobs and wealth creation which will bring self-reliance and sufficiency as well as contributing to the growth and development of the economy in the country (Isaac, 2018).

Technical skills are sets of abilities or knowledge used to perform practical tasks in areas of sciences, technology, engineering, and mathematics. In most cases, the acquisition of advanced technical skills requires specialized training or education which takes both time and resources. By providing technical skills training to the youths, you are instilling self confidence that they have the knowledge and competence to perform activities leading to self-reliant. Technical skills are skills, expertise or technical competence related to the field of the work whether engineering or technical. Technical skills are often associated with the use of tools, equipment related to work properly and efficiently, as well as technical matters. It can be known and understood more easily as can be seen clearly with naked eye. (Danjuma & Rebecca, 2017).

Technical skills are specialized knowledge and expertise needed to accomplish complex action task and process relating to computation and physical technology that demands creativity and talent. Technical skills therefore make individuals to be more effective, creative, productive, engaged, self-confidence because individual have the training and skills to and competence to perform practical work to the best of their ability. It is however, pointed that technical skills are a type of solution to understand the impact of practical engineering ability in societal and environmental contexts to demonstrate knowledge of and need for sustainable development (Abayomi & Odozi, 2014).

The ability to innovate is represented by the ability to continuously transform knowledge on technical and ideas into new fabrication, services, processes and system to the benefit of entrepreneur and the shareholders. The significant factor behind any business success is the mindset and the ability of youth to gain technical skills. The innovative power of any business depends on the quality of technical skills acquired by the personnel working in a given enterprise.

2.1.4 Self Employment

The creation of job can be possible if the candidates or youth has the required skills needed to create and secure either the industrial settings or become self-reliant individual. Job in the real sense is created for those that need it, desire it and can effectively perform the expected skills to achieve the objectives of the employer (Gabriel, 2019). job is the life line of any economy. Human development will definitely be grossly undermined and impaired without employment (Obiajulu, 2017). How soon Nigeria sets to

address the problems of mass unemployment, low productivity and poverty to a large extent depends on how speedily it is able to develop the millions of it youths into a knowledgeable and skilled people needed for the required change (Onuma, 2016).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The Refugee Effect

This study anchored on the Refugee effect theory which is considered as a theoretical stance from the effort to deflate unemployment and joblessness phenomena among people through entrepreneurship and skill acquisition programme. This theoretical assumption can be traced back to the work of Oxenfeldt (1943), who submitted that people who are challenged with joblessness, unemployment and low prospects for securing income and wage employment frequently move to self-employment as a workable option. This ideology was also found in Knights (1921) view that people are bound to make decision within three issues- unemployment, self-employment and employment (Solaja&Adenuga, 2016). Furthermore, the simple theory of income choice emphasized that refugee effect of unemployment will translate to increase in start-up business activity based on the assumption that the opportunity cost of starting a firm will enlarge. Evans and Leighton, (1990) supported this theoretical postulation in which that posited that unemployment is positively connected with the tendency to instigate new firm. Therefore, increase unemployment rate serves as a catalyst for business initiatives, business concept innovation and start-up intentions in any given society. In this avenue, some scholars believed creation of new business, innovation will require more employees to work which invariably translate to decrease in joblessness, poverty and unemployment rate (Chiekezie et al, 2016).

The relevance and application of the refugee effect theory to the study lies in its contributions to the idea of deflating unemployment and joblessness among the youth through viable skill acquisition programme. The theory explains how people who are challenged with joblessness and low prospect of securing income wage employment move to self-employment.

2.3 Empirical Review

Oguchi (2020) examined entrepreneurship innovation and skill acquisition as drivers of technological development in Nigeria. Specifically, it examined the significance of entrepreneurship innovation and skill acquisition in the process of technological advancement in Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Data were sourced through both primary and secondary sources. Data generated were analyzed using content analysis. The study revealed that innovation and skill acquisition could spur entrepreneurial development among teeming youths and technological advancement. The study concluded that skill acquisition is a veritable tool for employment sustainability. Based on the findings, the study recommends that government should fund skill acquisition agenda in Nigeria to achieve economic development.

Gabriel (2019). investigated acquisition of entrepreneurial and scientific skills for youth self-sustainability and job creation towards national development in Nigeria. Specifically, it aims to access the impact of entrepreneurial and scientific skill acquisition on youth self- sustainability and job creation in Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design. Data generated were analyzed using theoretical and content analysis. The study found that skill acquisition, entrepreneurial and scientific skills influence youth sustainability and job creation in Nigeria. The study concludes that skill acquisition and scientific skills serve as engine room for creativity, innovation and development. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that government should focus on its attention on improving scientific and practical skills training among the youth in Nigeria.

Jacob (2019), examined the effect of entrepreneurship on economic sustainability in South-East Nigeria. The study employed Ex-post factor research design. Data generated were analyzed using ordinary least square method of regression. The study revealed that infrastructural development and entrepreneurship contributed to economic sustainability. The study concludes that entrepreneurship has significant impact

on economic sustainability in South-East Nigeria. The study recommends that the scope of training should include technical, managerial and business skills.

Akinyele, Esther and Jaiyeola (2019) investigated entrepreneurial skill acquisition in soap making production among Abeokuta Nigeria, with the aim of examining the relationship between skill acquisition and SMEs productivity in Abeokuta. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Structured questionnaire was used to gather relevant data from a sample size of 126 SMEs. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson Correlation. From the analysis, it was found that there is significant relationship between skill acquisition and employment generation. The study conclude that skills acquisition serves as a catalyst for SMEs development and employment in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that sound skill entrepreneurship centers should be provided to support business startup and creativity in our institutions.

Anigbogu, Onwuteaka and Okoli (2019), investigated Igbo man perspective of apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development in South-East, Nigeria. The study aims to access the relationship between Igbo apprenticeship system and entrepreneurial development in South-East Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Data were gathered from a sample size of 482 SMEs owners. Data generated was analyzed using regression model of the least square. The study found that there is significant and positive relationship between Igbo man apprenticeship system and entrepreneurial development in South-East Nigeria. The study therefore conclude that apprenticeship system of Igbo contributes to enterprising ability of Igbos in Nigeria.

Onyeizugbe, Orogbu and Oyigbo (2018) investigated Entrepreneurial development and job creation in selected local government area in Enugu state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examines the extent to which innovativeness affects youth empowerment in the selected Local Government Area of Enugu state. The study adopted correlation research design. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to analyze data. The study found that innovativeness has no significant relationship with youth employment. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the government, should genuinely recognize the essence of entrepreneurship, job creation and innovation to economic development by providing the enabling environment for youths to be gainfully employed for economic development.

Steve (2010) investigated critical thinking in entrepreneurial and youths' attitude towards skill acquisition in Nigeria. The study aimed at examining the attitude of Nigerian youths towards entrepreneurship development. The study employed descriptive survey design. Inferential statistics and regression analysis was used for analysis and hypothesis testing. It was found that critical thinking entrepreneurs have significant and positive inference on youths' attitude towards skill acquisition and help in entrepreneurial development among the youth in Plateau state. The study concludes that critical thinking entrepreneurship contributes to youth attitudes towards risk taking and innovation. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the government should provide an enabling environment to help in improving the attitude of youths towards entrepreneurial development.

Danjuma and Rebecca (2017) examined skill acquisition for wealth creation of youths in Agidi Development Area, Nasarawa State, Nigeria with the objective of investigating how the youths can create wealth through entrepreneurship skills. The study adopted descriptive research design. Mean rating, standard deviation and T-test was used for data analysis. The study found that most youths in Agidi lack sufficient entrepreneurial skills and mindset of self-employment before coming out from the tertiary institutions in Nasarawa state. The study concludes that skill acquisition has not been given the required attention in most higher institutions in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the government should ensure the provision of viable and functional entrepreneurship centres in all higher institutions in the state.

Maryrose and Obiajulu (2017) examined acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills in basic sciences for job creation in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aimed to investigate how skill acquisition and innovative skills help in bridging the gap between the school and labour market where the learner will work after graduation so as to be self-reliant. The study employed descriptive survey research design. Mean and standard deviation was used for data presentation while Pearson correlation was used for test of

hypotheses and analysis. The study revealed that lots of skills were needed in science education for job creation. The study recommends that teachers should use practically oriented methods in teaching the students.

Chiekezie, Nzewi and Iyekekpolor (2016) investigated entrepreneurial skills acquisition and job creation in Benin City, Nigeria. The study aims to examine the extent of the relationships between entrepreneurial skill acquisition and job creation. The study employed descriptive survey design. Data generated were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient with the aid of SPSS version 21. It was revealed that acquisition of entrepreneurial skills is an indispensable means of making jobs available in Benin City, Nigeria. Based on the finding, the study recommends that there should be improved practical programmes in school curriculum, creating awareness through entrepreneurial skill training classes, seminars conferences and workshop.

Table 2.3.1 Webometric table

S/ N	AUTHOR/YEAR	TOPIC	VARIABLE	METHODOLOGY	FINDINGS/ CONCLUSION
1	Oguchi (2020)	Entrepreneurship innovation and skill acquisition as drivers of technological development in Nigeria	Innovation, Skill acquisition, Technological Development	Descriptive survey method	Innovation and skill acquisition could spur entrepreneurship development among teeming youths and technological advancement
2	Gabriel (2019)	Acquisition of entrepreneurial and scientific skills for youth's self-sustainability and job creation towards national development in Nigeria.	Entrepreneurial skills, Job creation, national Development, scientific skills self-sustainability	Descriptive research design	Skill acquisition, entrepreneurial and scientific skills influence youth's sustainability and job creation in Nigeria.
3	Jacob (2019)	Effect of Entrepreneurship on economic sustainability in South East Nigeria.	Entrepreneurship, Infrastructural development, economic sustainability.	Ex-post factor Research design and Ordinary Least Square regression method	The study found that infrastructural development and entrepreneurship contributed to economic development.
4	Akinyele, Esther and Jaiyecola (2019)	Entrepreneurial skill acquisition in soap making production among SMEs in Abeokuta Nigeria.	Skill acquisition, Productivity, SMEs	Descriptive survey research design, descriptive statistics and Pearson Correlation	There is significant relationship between skill acquisition and employment generation
5	Anigbogu, Onwuteaka, and Okoli (2019)	Igbo man perspective of apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria	Apprenticeship, entrepreneurial development	Descriptive survey design and regression model of Least square method.	There is significant positive relationship between Igbo man apprenticeship system and entrepreneurial

					development in South East Nigeria.
6	Onyeizugbe, Orogbu and Oyigbo (2018)	Entrepreneurial development and job creation in selected Local Government Areas in Enugu state, Nigeria.	Entrepreneurial development, Job creation, Innovativeness, Empowerment	Correlation research design and Pearson correlation coefficient.	The study found that innovativeness has no significant relationship with youth employment.
7	Steve (2010)	Critical thinking in entrepreneurial and youth's attitude towards entrepreneurial skill acquisition in Nigeria	Skill acquisition, critical thinking, attitude,	Descriptive survey, inferential statistics and Regression analysis	It was found that critical thinking entrepreneurs have significant and positive inference on youth attitude towards skill acquisition and help in entrepreneurial development among the youths in plateau state.
8	Danjuma and Rebecca (2017)	Skill acquisition for wealth creation of youths in Agidi Development Area, Nassarawa state, Nigeria.	Skill acquisition, wealth creation, entrepreneurial skills.	Descriptive research design. T-test, mean and standard deviation	The findings revealed that most youths in Agidi lack sufficient entrepreneurial skills and mindset of self-employment before coming out from tertiary institutions.
9	Maryrose and Obianuju (2017)	Acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills in basic science for job creation in Nigeria	Entrepreneurial skills, innovative skills, job creation	Descriptive survey research design. Mean and standard deviation, Pearson correlation	The findings revealed that lots of skills were needed in science education for job creation.
10	Chiekezie, Nzewi and Iyekekpolor	Entrepreneurial skills acquisition and job creation in Benin City, Nigeria.	Entrepreneurial skills, job creation	Descriptive survey design, Pearson correlation coefficient	The study found that acquisition of entrepreneurial skills is an indispensable means of making jobs available in Benin City, Nigeria.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey research design. The purpose is to generate detailed and factual information that describe the existing phenomenon. Descriptive survey was adopted because it minimizes the possibility of bias. It is useful when the data are collected or described persons, organizations settings or phenomenon (Creswell 2003). It is further employed because data are collected directly from the participants

3.2 Area of the Study

The study area covered Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of youths in Awka South Local government Area of Anambra State that have participated in one form of skill acquisition programme or the other that was organized by the government and non-governmental agencies and are equally registered with the youth leader. The total population is 3180 youths.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

Cooper and Schindler (2003), state that the size of a sample should be a function of the variation in the population parameter under the study and the estimate precision needed by the researcher. The target population of the youth is 3180. The statistical formula devised by Taro Yamane (1967) was employed to determine the sample size. Thus Taro Yamani formular: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

Where

n = Sample size

N = Population Size (3180)

E = Element of Error (0.05)

1 = Constant

Using the formula or the above equation, the sample size is:

$$n = \frac{3180}{1+3,180(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3180}{1+3180(0.0025)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3180}{1+7.95}$$

$$n = \frac{3180}{8.95}$$

$$n = 355.3$$

$$n = 355.$$

3.5 Sample Technique

Simple random sampling technique was employed because the population is known, identified, accessible and finite. This also ensure objectivity and minimizes bias.

3.6 Sources of Data

The study used both primary and secondary sources. Primary sources which consists of raw data generated from responses of questionnaire by the respondents while secondary sources include internet material, and other already made information

3.7 Method of Data Collection

The study adopted the use of structured questionnaire on a five-pointlikert scale of strongly agreed, agreed, undecided, disagreed and strongly disagree to gather necessary data from the sampled respondents. The questionnaire is divided into two sections, A and B. Section A deals with the personal data of the respondents while section B contains research statements postulated in line with the research questions.

3.8 Validity of the Instrument

The study used face and content validity. The instrument was first given to two lecturers in Entrepreneurship Studies Department for validation before the supervisor finally face validated it. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire. The questionnaire is attached as an appendix to this work.

3.9 Reliability of the Instrument

Table 3.1 Reliability Test (Cronbach’s Alpha for measure of Variables.

Variable	Item no.	Cronbach’s Alpha
Skill Acquisition	5	0.85
Entrepreneurial Development	5	0.76

Source: SPSS Software Version 23

Cronbach’s alpha coefficient, provides the most ranges from 0 to 1. the higher the coefficient, the more reliable are the items in measuring the constructs. A value below 0.6 generally indicates unsatisfactory internal consistency and reliability. Ideally, Cronbach’s coefficient of a scale should be above 0.7Pallant (2001). This indicates that the questions were consistent and highly reliable since it fell within the range (0.76 and 0.85 percent respectively).

3.10 Method of Data Analysis.

The data generated were presented using descriptive statistics while hypothesis was tested using multiple regression method with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.1.1: Returned and Unreturned Questionnaire

	Frequency	Percentage
Returned Questionnaire (Valid)	286	80.56
Returned Questionnaire (Invalid)	21	5.92
Unreturned Questionnaire	48	13. 52
Total Questionnaire Administered	355	100

Source: Field survey (2022)

Table 4.2: Demographic of the Respondents

Variables		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Female	118	41.3
	Male	168	58.7
Age	18-23	39	13.6
	24-29	54	18.9
	30-35	90	31.5
	36-39	63	22
	40-and above	40	14
Educational Status	Educated	226	79
	None Educated	60	21

Source: SPSS Version 23

Table 4.1.2 above shows that respondents in this study are mostly male (58.7%) while the female represent 41.3%. Age bracket within 36-39 years dominate the respondents and educational status of the respondents shows that 226 respondents representing 79% of the population are educated.

Research Question 1: *To what extent does technical skill training affect entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria?*

SN	Variable	SA	A	I	D	SD	Remarks
1	Youths love to participate in technical skill acquisition training in Anambra state	138 (58.7%)	35 (38.7%)	22 (6.0%)	-	-	Agreement
2	Goal and objectives of technicalskill acquisition training will make one	145 (61.7%)	50 (38.3%)	-	-	-	Agreement

	self-reliant and productivity						
3	Technical skill acquisition training is the key to economic empowerment among youths in Anambra state.	40 (36.2%)	115 (48.9%)	20 (2.6%)	15 (10.6%)	5 (1.7%)	Agreement
4	Parental negative attitude toward technical and vocational Education (TVE) has given room for entrepreneurial development among youths.	110 (57.9%)	61 (32.8%)	10 (3.8%)	9 (3.4%)	5 (2.1%)	Agreement

Source: Computation from SPSS 23 Analysis

The remarks as shown in table 4.2 indicate the overall decision of the respondents on each of the question items (row) in the table. Youths love to participate in entrepreneurship activities in Anambra state. Again, the respondents believed Goal and objectives of technical skill acquisition will make one self-reliant and productivity. Majority of the youths also believed that technical skill acquisition is the key to economic empowerment among youths in Anambra state. And also, the youths believed that Parental negative attitude toward technical and vocational Education (TVE) has given room for entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does youth empowerment affect entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria?*

SN	Variable	SA	A	I	D	SD	Remarks
5	Youth empowerment is that tendency of equipping and making youths experts in the production of certain items	126 (53.6%)	50 (41.3%)	19 (5.1%)	-	-	Agreement
6	Role of youth empowerment is that tendency of equipping and making students experts in the production of certain items	109 (63.4%)	74 (31.5%)	12 (5.1%)	-	-	Agreement
7	Youth empowerment can greatly help in addressing the level of poverty among youths through employable job	90 (54.5%)	70 (34.9%)	25 (6.4%)	10 (4.3%)		Agreement
8	Youth empowerment involves a systematic search for an analysis of opportunities.	95 (57.9%)	91 (38.7%)	9 (3.8%)	-	-	Agreement

Source: Computation from SPSS 23 Analysis

The results of table 4.3 revealed that youths are of the view that youth empowerment is that tendency of equipping and making students experts in the production of certain items. The study made it clear that Role of youth empowerment is that tendency of equipping and making students experts in the production of certain items. In addition, it is obvious that youth empowerment can greatly help in addressing the

level of poverty among youths through employable job. Furthermore, the respondents believed that youth empowerment involves a systematic search for an analysis of opportunities.

Research Question 3: *To what degree does infrastructural development affect entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria?*

SN	Variable	SA	A	I	D	SD	Remarks
9	Government should not be lukewarm towards the provision of the needed infrastructures in Anambra state.	161 (68.5%)	26 (11.1%)	12 (5.1%)	28 (11.9%)	8 (3.4%)	Agreement
10	Lack of personnel, Equipment and material is problem associated to Entrepreneurial development in Anambra state	127 (54%)	96 (40.9%)	12 (5.1%)	-	-	Agreement
11	If Nigeria will achieve the Sustainable development goals (SDGs)infrastructural development is the key.	142 (60.4%)	72 (30.6%)	21 (8.9%)	-	-	Agreement
12	The easy way to reduce unemployment among youths in Anambra state is through the provision of adequate infrastructure.	85 (36.2%)	62 (26.4%)	11 (4.7%)	40 (17.0%)	37 (15.7%)	Agreement

Source: Computation from SPSS 23 Analysis

The respondents are of the opinion that Government should not be lukewarm towards the provision of the needed infrastructures in Anambra State. The above table also revealed that Lack of personnel, Equipment and material is problem associated to youths' attitudes toward Entrepreneurial development. Again, the study shows that If Nigeria will achieve the sustainable development goals (SDGs) then infrastructural development is the key. Also, the youths believed that the easy way to reduce unemployment among graduates is the teaching and learning of Entrepreneurship Education in school.

4.2 Analysis of Data (Hypotheses Testing)

Regression analysis was used to test the formulated hypotheses. The results of the hypotheses test were interpreted accordingly;

Ho₁: Technical Skill acquisition has no significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.259 ^a	.211	.303	3.67231

a. Predictors: (Constant), Technical skill acquisition

The model summary table above shows the R to be at .259, R square at .211, adjusted R square at .303 while std error of the estimate at 3.67231. The table reveal that the R square being at .211 does not strongly determine the extent to which the independent variable affects the dependent variable.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	177.612	1	177.612	34.871	.000 ^b
	Residual	664.135	194	7.141		
	Total	841.747	195			

a. Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Technical skill acquisition

The Anova table above show that the F value is at 34.871 and the sig level is at .000 which is lesser than .05, that is the probability level. This signifies that there is significant factors that technical skill acquisition has significant effects on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria. The null hypothesis is rejected

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.296	.926		7.721	.000
	factor that hinder	.531	.106	.459	5.987	.000

a. Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial development

The coefficient table above shows the significant level of t statistics which reveals that the t value is at 4.987 and the sig level at .000. This means that there is significant level of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

H₂: Youth empowerment does not affect entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.062 ^a	.004	-.007	5.00447

a. Predictors: (Constant), youth empowerment

The table above shows that the R is at .062, R square is at .004, Adjusted R square at -.007 while std. error of the estimate at 5.00447. This shows that the R square being at .004 does not a strong determinant of the independent variable over dependent variable.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.252	1	2.252	4.549	.000 ^b
	Residual	839.495	194	9.027		
	Total	841.747	195			

a. Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial development

b. Predictors: (Constant), youth empowerment.

The anova table above shows that the F statistics at 4.549 and the significant level at .000 which is lesser than the probability of .05. This therefore means that youth empowerment affects entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.314	1.256		8.209	.000
	farctor that enhance	-.065	.129	-.052	-.499	.619

a. Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial development

The coefficient table above shows that the t value is at 8.209 and sig value is at .000. which signifies that there is significant of the independent variable over the dependent variable.

H₃: infrastructural development has no significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.034 ^a	.001	-.010	3.00680

a. Predictors: (Constant), infrastructural development

The table above shows the R at .034, R square at .001, adjusted R square at -.010, while std error of the estimate at 3.00680. This reveals that R square being at .001 is not a good determinant of the strength of the independent variable over the dependent variable

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.950	1	.950	4.105	.000 ^b
	Residual	840.798	93	9.041		
	Total	841.747	94			

a. Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial development

b. Predictors: (Constant), infrastructural development

The Anova table above shows that the f value is at 4.105 and the sig is at .000 which is lesser than the probability level of .05. This means that infrastructural development has significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state Nigeria. Null hypothesis is rejected

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.385	1.036		9.060	.000
	insufficient finance	.037	.116	.034	.324	.747

a. Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial development

The coefficient table above shows that the t value is 9.060 while the sig value is .000 which is lesser than the probability level of .05. This reveals that there is significant of the independent variable over the dependent variable.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study aimed at finding out the effect skill acquisition on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state Nigeria. However, the following are the summary of the major findings;

1. Skill acquisition has significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state Nigeria
2. Entrepreneurship empowerment affects entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state Nigeria
3. Infrastructural development has significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state Nigeria

5.2 Conclusions

Unemployment among Nigerian graduates has weakened the national economy as individuals are unable to contribute to the economy. Nigeria has a history of economic stagnation that has led to decline in white collar jobs. The inclusion of entrepreneurial course in all disciplines will to a great extent, assist in solving these problems of high unemployment and underemployment. Skill acquisition has been recognized as a catalyst to speed up the employment opportunities as this will exposed and encourage youths to startup businesses and improve business potentials among them. An effective strategy to develop the indigenous private sector and reduce unemployment among Nigerian graduates is through skill acquisitionThe study aimed at finding out the effect of skill acquisition on entrepreneurial

development among youths in Anambra state. The inferential statistical data analysis provided evidence of existing relationships amongst the variables. The conclusions derived from the study are that skill acquisition has significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Youth empowerment affects entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, infrastructural development has significant effect on entrepreneurial development among youths in Anambra state, Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

In the light of the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The government should organize and carry out sustainable awareness campaign to promote technical skill training in all parts of the country with sincerity and objectivity, devoid of political interest so as to motivate the youths towards becoming job providers instead of job seekers.
- ii. There should be adequate empowerment for youths that have acquired the necessary skills
- iii. The government should provide the needed infrastructures in place to enable the youths to thrive in their entrepreneurial ventures.

REFERENCES

- Akinyele, S. T., Akinyele, E.F &Jaiyeola R. A (2019). Entrepreneurial skills acquisition in soap making production among small scale enterprises performance in Abeokuta, Nigeria. *Journal of management Science and Entrepreneurship*. 19(7), 241-250.
- Anigbogu, T. U., Onwuteaka, I. C., &Okoli, I. M.(2019).Southeast The Igbo man perspectives of apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development in South East Nigeria.: Implication of economic growth. *International Journal of research and innovation in applied science (IJRIAS) IV*, 91-94
- Bala, D (2020). Training and skill development for improving employees' productivity in listed deposit money bank in Nigeria. *Journal of vocational and technical educators*. 5(5), 179-182
- Chiekezie, O. M., Nzewi, H. N &Erhinmwionose, I. A (2016). Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition and Job Creation in Benin City, Nigeria. *EPR international Journal of economic and business review*. 4(6). 94-98
- Danjuma, A.O & Rebecca , I. U (2017). Entrepreneurship skill acquisition for wealth creation of youths in Agidi development Area of Nassarawa State. *International Journal of Academic*. 4(1), 1-7
- Efe-Imafidon E. O, Ade-Adenyi, O, Umukoro, E, &Ajitemisan, M. (2017). Entrepreneurial Skill Acquisition as a facilitator of self employability among Nigeria Youths. *Covenant Journal of Entrepreneurship*. (CJOE), 1(2), 10-13
- Essay, U. K (2018). The importance of developing entrepreneurship skills commerce essay. Retrieved on 3/2/2022 from <http://www.ukessay.com/essay/com>.
- Gabriel, O.A (2019). Acquisition of Entrepreneurial and Scientific Skill for Youths Sustainability and Job Creation towards National Development in Nigeria. *World Journal of Entrepreneurial Development Studies*. 3(1) 24-27
- Isaac, I.A, Falilat, A.A, Oladipo, G.T &Omotoya, O. O (2018). Effect of Entrepreneurship skills development on Youths Employment in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economic and Business Research* (2), 125-130
- Jacobs, C. J (2019). Entrepreneurship on Economic Sustainability in South East, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business system and economics*. 12(3), 16-19
- Iyaji, S.O, Achoba, M.I & Kolawole, O.B (2018). the Role of Vocational Skills Acquisition in Reducing Unemployment among architecture graduates in Nigeria. *Journal of good governance and sustainable development in Africa (JGGSDA)*, 4(2)146-153.
- Maryrose, C. M &Obiajuru, C.E (2017). Acquisition of Innovative and Entrepreneurial Skills in Basic Science Education Among the Youths in Kano State. *Journal of Science Education International*. 28(3) 207-209.

- Muhammed, B. A (2016). Impact of Entrepreneurship Development Programme on Income and Employment Generation among the Youths in Kano State. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities*. 6(4), 254-256.
- Oboreh, J. C & Nnebe, E. G (2019), Entrepreneurship Education and Skills Acquisition of graduates in Public Universities South-East, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Law Research*. 7(4) 84-89.
- Oguchi, C.B (2020). Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Skill Acquisition as Drivers of Technological Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development, Education and Science Research*. 6(1) 39-43
- Olatunji, Y. A. (2016). Entrepreneurship and Small Scale Business Enterprises Development in Nigeria. Ibadan University Press.
- Onuma, N. (2016), Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institution: A Remedy to Graduates Unemployment. *British Journal of Education* 4(5), 16-21.
- Onyeizugbe, C. U, Orogbu, O.L & Oyigbo, M.C (2018). Entrepreneurial Development and Job Creation in Selected Local Government Areas in Enugu state, Nigeria. *International Journal of management Studies and Research (IJMSR)*. 3(7), 41-47.
- Onugu, J. J & Nafim, A. T (2014). An Exploratory Study of Igbo Entrepreneurial activity and business success in Nigeria as the panacea for economic growth and development. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*. 3(9) 158.
- Oxenfeldt, A. (1943). *New Firms and Free Enterprise*, Wahington D. C: American Council on Public Affairs
- Paul, B. (2017). Assessing Entrepreneurship Education for Skill Acquisition and Job Generation by Business Education student in Bayelsa state., Nigeria. *International Journal of education, culture and society*. 2(1) 1-4
- Pfeiffer, F. & Reize, F (2000). Business Start-ups by the Unemployment-An Economic Analysis Based on Firm data, *Labour Economics*, 7 (5), 629-642.
- Riti, J. S, & Kamah, M. (2015). Entrepreneurship, Employment and Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and management Science*. 4(1), 179-182.
- Schumpeter, J. A (1934). *The theory of Economic Development*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press (New-York: Oxford University Press 1961.
- Solaja, O. M & Adenuga, O. A (2016). Investigating the Impact of Skill Acquisition Dilemma in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. 2(2) 16- 21
- Steve, A. D (2018). Critical Thinking Entrepreneurship and Youth Attitudes Towards Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition in Plateau State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Research*. 9(1). 87-93.
- Sule, M. (2019). The role of Entrepreneurship Education on Job Creation Among Youths in Nigeria. *International letters social humanistic sciences* 15(1).
- Umunadi, E. K. (2015). Acquisition of skills and Competences by Technical Education Teachers and Instrument for National Growth in Nigeria. *Journal of qualitative Education*. 6(1), 1- 9.